

.THE IMPORTANCE OF KEEPING SCHOOL RECORDS IN UBE SCHOOLS

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Abstract

The paper was written to emphasis the importance of record keeping in school under the universal basic education. The mode and methods used by teachers in keeping school records was look into in this paper. The paper classified school records into two parts; the administrative records kept by the head teachers and the class records kept by the class teachers. It showed that most of the school records that are kept by the head teachers and class teachers. were not kept appropriately It was therefore suggested that government, private agencies and other stakeholders involved in the educational programmes should constantly organize seminal for head teachers and teachers in order to update their knowledge of keeping school records.

Introduction

Education can be defined as a means of developing human resources by cultivating appropriate skills, knowledge and attitudes without which the nation cannot harness resources to industrialize and take part in the global knowledge economy (Durosaro,2012).

The objectives of Universal Basic Education Programme (UBE) in 2014 edition include:

1. Provision of free education for the first nine years of schooling
2. Early childhood care and socialization.
3. Acquisition of functional literacy.
4. Reducing incidence of drop out in schools
5. To create strong consciousness for education among youth

School records are documents kept in the school either by the principal or class teacher to give information about the progress pupils or students and the school in general. School records can also be seen as document inside which the daily events, equipment, transactions, ceremonies and others that affect the school are recorded. Proper keeping of school record enable both head teacher and class teachers discharge their duties efficiently and effectively. Generally, school records contribute immensely towards proper performance of the various function of the school system. Other functions performed by the school record according to Salau and Oyedepo (2016) are:.

1. Helping the head teacher and the teacher to understand the background nature, problems, activities and progress of each child.
2. Furnishing the parents with data and the activities, problems and achievement of their children.
3. Providing the pupils or students with information on the pattern of their progress. Enabling the prospective employers to gather information on the background, nature, activities and achievement of applicants. Helping to determine whether no student should be accepted or transferred to school they seek transfer.
4. Serving as crucial factors to the successful planning of the finance. Physical and human resources in the school system by the ministry of education and other relevant agencies.

Statement of the Problem

Despite the importance of school records in the achievement of educational objectives, these records do not seem to be adequately managed by schools head. From observation, reliable records are not properly managed. This suggests that records management practice in Nigeria has a number of problems which may include insufficient skilled and experienced record management personnel and possibly low priority attention to records management in the scheme of things. This low priority attention to records management often manifest on the area of missing files and records, falsification of records (change of declaration of age), missing school plan and destruction of records to cover up something. Despite the core value of effective record keeping in school system, many ube schools head teacher have complained of falsification of data among staff, and several time, supervisors from state ministry of education and local government education authority have also recorded high falsification of school data by school heads and teachers most often do not provide accurate number of students on enrolment during P.T.A levy account, among others.

Purpose of Study

The main purpose of this study was to investigate the importance of school records in ube schools. Specifically, the study:

- (1) Found out what school records that are presently kept in ube schools.
- (2) Found out the problems associated with keeping of school records.

School records can be divided into two viz:

Administrative records and class records

Administrative Records

These are records specially kept by the head teacher or a person so delegated. Such administrative records are kept in the head teachers' office for security purpose. Administrative records kept by schools include educational laws, teacher's manual,

log book, administrative register, visitor's book, corporal punishment book, honour's roll, transfer certificate book, staff casual leave book, staff lesson attendance book, school time table, no on roll board, time book, staff movement book, suggestion file, school budget, school inventory! stock book, staff maternity file, staff meeting book, PTA accounts! Financial books, staff instruction book, PTA minutes book, and school health book. Ogunsanju (2006)

Education Law: This is available in the ministry of education. It contains the objective and policies of the government on education and education strategies. It stipulates the rights of teachers and rights of pupils students. Every school should compulsorily obtain a copy of education law so that both the head teacher and class teachers will be conversant with its contents.

Teachers Manual: This record centre's on teacher's certification, different categories of teachers, duties of school head, teacher's discipline and fringe benefits such as maternity leave casual study leave, annual leave, leave allowance, responsibility allowance, transport allowance and others. This document enables teacher to know their obligations, rights and privileges. All teachers should have a copy of this document.

Log Book: This document is used to record all important activities in the life of the school. For example the day the school was established, holidays, seminars held, refresher courses, sandwich courses and workshops attended by members of staff of the school. It also contains information on appointments, transfers retirements and registration. The absence of a teacher in the school due to sickness or any other reasons that caused the teacher to be absent from the school is recorded in the book. Deaths of teachers and pupils or students are recorded in this book. Records of pupils or students with special academic performance who are given prizes annually are also recorded in the log book.

The books also contain information on school inspection's reports, final examination, suspension or expulsion of pupil and the book is signed and always locked. The book is important because it gives information about the history of the school, gives aspirations, problems and achievements of the school.

Sample of Log Book

DATE.....EVENT.....SIGNATURE AND DATE.....

4/10/20	First set of 40 students admitted into form 1	
28/10/20	Commissioning of first block of classroom by the Commissioner for Education	
29/10/20	First set of government teachers sent from the ministry	
21/10/20	First PTA meeting with the principal official appointed.	

Admission Register: This book contains the name of every student admitted into the school. The details about each child is recorded, this include admission number, name, sex, date of birth, date of admission, names and addresses of parents, Occupation of parents, promotion/repetition/ withdrawal/transfer/completion of course.

Admission	Name	Sex	Date of Birth	Admission date	Name of Parent	Occupation	1 st	2 nd	3 rd	4 th
001	Ojo James	M	1/6/20	2/2/19						
002	Ade Ade	M	1/9/20	30/4/19						
003	Sunday Sunday	M	2/5/20	2/2/20						

Visitor's Book: This Book is to be signed by all important personalities that visit the school. Information to be filled by the visitors includes name and addresses of visitors, date, purpose, remark and signature. Comments of visitors at times help in shaping and raising the standard of the school. As a matter of respect a page is always reserved for important personalities like head of states, governors, Obas, Bishop who seldom visit the schools. No other person is allowed to sign on the same page used by them.

Corporal Punishment: This book is used in recording very serious offences committed by the students. The punishment book serves as guide to reduce the incidence of unreasonable behaviours in school. At times it helps schools to have insight into knowing suspects whenever there is any problem in the school. A punishment book should contain the name of the student, sex, age, type of offence, class, date, time, type of punishment administered and the signature of the teacher that gave the punishment.

B. Class Records

These are the records kept by the class teacher. Majority of the records are kept and operated on frequent basis, while others are used occasionally. To some

extent the mode and nature of these records are kept by the teacher portrays the type of teacher an individual is, therefore these records are to be kept neatly and carefully. Some officials at times pick these records to assess the teachers without informing them. Examples of such class records are attendance register, student progress report card, lesson note, master report sheet progress, syllabus, progress chart, unit plan, class time-table, record of work, class inventory/stock book, marks book, class indicator, and scheme of work. Oyedeji (2006).

Class Attendance Register: This is one of the important class records kept by the teacher. This record must be filled neatly, accurately and honestly by the class teacher. Every child should be seen before he/she is marked present.

Every student should be seen physically. Class teachers can be implicated and charged for conspiracy, if any student commits criminal offence. At the end of the term, all the calculations should be done and the register closed appropriately. The register is to be marked at the beginning of each class session either in the morning or in the afternoon.

At the end of the term, there is need for the class teacher to calculate average attendance for term which could be gotten through the use of this formula:

$$\text{AV Attendance per term} = \frac{\text{Total attendance for term}}{\text{No of pupils or student}}$$

$$\text{AND NOT: } \frac{\text{Total attendance for term}}{\text{No of times school opened}}$$

Lesson Note: This is the document prepared by the teacher to guide the teacher in teaching learning process. No unit is considered properly taught unless the teaching is guided by a thoroughly prepared lesson note. Hence, note of lesson is regarded as one of the most important documents kept by the class teacher. An ideal lesson note must contain the following parts:

- 1) Date
- 2) Name of Teacher
- 3) School
- 4) Subject
- 5) Class
- 6) Average Age
- 7) No of Student
- 8) Period:
- 9) Topic: Athletics/Circle
- 10) Sub-Topic: Sprint Start/Area of Circle
- 11) Instructional Materials/Teaching Aid:-
- 12) Reference Materials: Ajadi T. A. (2021). The Introduction to mathematics for Economics, Ilorin: Nigeria.

- 13) **Instructional Objective:** to teach the pupils area of a circle
- 14) **Performance Objectives:** At the end of the lesson the student should be able to:
 - a. State the formulae for area of a circle
 - b. Apply the formulae to find the area of a circle
- 15) **Entry Behaviour/Previous Knowledge:** State what the student have learnt before, that will aid the teaching on what in your opinion is relevant to the topic which students have come across.
- 16) **Instructional Procedures:** Step 1: Introduce the lesson by asking the students some questions on their previous knowledge. Step 2: introduce the day's topic as it is expected making use of the instructional materials and giving necessary examples that can complement the lesson. This aspect should be written properly in order to enable any other teacher teach the topic when the teacher is indisposed to teach the lesson.
- 17) **Evaluation:** Evaluate your lesson. Write out the questions you expected the student to answer and the answers to be given by the students.
- 18) **Conclusion:** Teacher uses the answers given by the students to form of chalkboard summary.
- 19) **Assignment:** Write out the questions to be done by students from home.

Mark's Book: This is the book in which the marks scored by students are recorded. It is the duty of each subject/class teacher to keep a book in which he records students' marks. The teacher writes the names of the students offering the subjects and records their scores for each continuous assessment and examination. It is from this book that marks are transferred into report card of students. If any error is discovered in the report cards, the original score could be traced in the marks book.

Student Report Cards: This is the document in which score of each subject recorded. This document should be filled carefully and neatly by the teachers because the mode of filling the report card tells more about the teacher. Like time school opened and number of times attended by students should be transferred properly. Teachers' comments should be directed toward psychomotor and affective domains while cognitive domain should be done by the head-teacher or any other person delegated to do so. For example, teachers' comments should include: Tunji is a truant/regular, late comer and others to list few and not Tunji needs improve in English Language. This is meant for head teacher who may not even know the student.

By mentioning the name of the student, you are showing that you actually know the student. Avoid the use of pronoun like him or her when writing comments. Student can easily debunk the comment when their names are not written. It is important to note that teacher often commit errors of omission, poor expressions or wrong calculations when making entries into the report card. Such lapses make parent lose confidence in the quality of instructions given by the school. The student report card should indicate grades score by the student in each subject's positions in each subject, and should also contain overall position.

Master Report Sheet: It is also called broad sheet. This is the document in which all the names of the students in the class are listed with their scores in each subject and overall positions are recorded. The master report sheet is very useful because at a glance it's very easy for individual to compare achievements of the students in all arms of the class. It helps the students to determine their position among the students in all arms of the class.

Problems Associated with Record Keeping in Schools

As important as information from school records are to effective administration of schools, effective record keeping in schools have many problems. Some of these problems include:

Inability to keep available records: High rate of pupils attrition especially in the rural areas poses a big problem. Children who are enrolled in school fall out of school at will, either through sheer lack of interest or ignorance of what school holds in stock for them in future. Ignorance, poor attitude of parents cause parents to withdraw their children from school without as much telling the headmaster. Infrastructure and equipment are destroyed from time to time by bush fire, rain storms, white ants and mischievous persons, including school pupils. All these contribute in no small measure in frustrating the efforts of the planner at acquiring valid and reliable data (Uwazurike 1991).

Poor Attitude of school personnel towards data collection: Despite the fact that teachers and principals are witnesses to the problems described above, they are many a time, uncooperative when records are demanded of them from time to time in respect of their schools. Rather than make effort, they copy out old records verbatim or amend them slightly and submit to the head office.

Shortage of staff: The section of the educational offices charged with collecting educational statistics is very often under staffed. As a result of the shortage in the number and quite often qualifications and experiences of such staff, they cannot cope with the volume of work before them. They do their best, but sometimes, their best falls short of the requirements of the planning office.

Lack of thorough supervision by the head teacher: This can arise if a teacher records topics not taught under record of work covered in the diary. It is unethical to record what has not been taught. Some teachers make false entries in the time book, and staff movement register because such records are not effectively monitored by the school head. Uwazurike(1991), maintained that untimely supply of records, lack of through supervision and funds, inadequate knowledge of record keeping, incessant alteration of records and role of conflict among school principals among others are the chief problems recorded to have associated with records keeping in school system.

Inadequate knowledge of record keepers for the use of information from records: If the information given are false or incomplete, it cannot give us the accurate information needed. Lack of thorough supervision by the head teacher, lead to destruction of poorly kept records by termites, flood or storm. This usually occurs as a result of keeping such records in wooden cup boards or on bare floors. Retrieval problems such as corruption of files by computer virus leading to distortion or complete erasure of stored data cause educational wastage.

Conclusion

This paper has been able to identify some records used in schools either administrative or classroom records. The writers only discussed few documents that are very paramount to day-to-day administration of the school and classroom teaching. It was also concluded that school records are very important and should be kept honestly, faithfully and accurately to avoid problems that may arise due to improper keeping of records. Head-teacher should therefore constantly check the records most especially the lesson plan in order to improve teaching-learning process in the Universal Basic Education programme. It will also justify the huge amount of money' expended on the UBE programme by the government.

Recommendations

The following recommendations are made:

1. Government should always organize refresher courses for head-teachers and teachers in order to update their knowledge of keeping school records.
2. Researchers should write more books on the aspect of keeping school records
3. Funds should be made available for researchers to carry out studies related to keeping of school records.

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